

and yttrium³ and malate complex of yttrium⁴ that,

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{TTML}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - a/b \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{Where, } a = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + 3 \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

$$\text{and } b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] = [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A$; $\Delta[\text{TTML}] = [\text{TTML}]_B - [\text{TTML}]_A$; $[\text{NaOH}]_A$, $[\text{NaOH}]_B$, $[\text{TTML}]_A$, $[\text{TTML}]_B$, $[\text{C}]$ and n are represented by molar concentrations of sodium hydroxide at Curve A and B, total thiomalate concentration at Curve A and B, thiomalate complex and the number of protons liberated per gm. atom of metal ion respectively. k_1 (2.291×10^{-4}), k_2 (2.291×10^{-5}) and k_3 (4.266×10^{-11}) are the first, second and third dissociation constants⁵ of thiomalic acid respectively.

When the formation of the complex is complete, $[\text{C}] = [\text{Metal Salt}]$

$$\text{Hence } \frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{TTML}]}{[\text{Metal Salt}]} = n - a/b \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of $\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$, $-\Delta[\text{TTML}]$, $[\text{Metal salt}]$ and then n were calculated at different pH values by the methods adopted earlier. The values of n are found to be less than 2 below pH 4.6, 5.8, 5.0, 4.8 and 4.6 for beryllium, manganese, cobalt, nickel and zinc respectively. Hence below these pH values a neutral complex C is formed in each case with liberation of two protons according to the equation

The concentration of complex C was calculated below these pH values by assuming n values to be 2, by the equation (4) and K values were calculated as before by the equation (2). The mean values of $-\log K$ are found to be 5.17 ± 0.11 , 5.91 ± 0.05 , 5.84 ± 0.09 , 5.48 ± 0.11 and 4.28 ± 0.16 for beryllium, manganese, cobalt, nickel and zinc thiomalate system respectively. The values of n are greater than 2 and less than 3 at and above pH 4.6, 5.8, 4.8 and 4.6 for beryllium, manganese, nickel and zinc respectively. Hence this indicates the dissociation of the neutral complex C, according to the equation (5)

The equilibrium constant K_1 can be represented by the equation (6)

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} \quad \dots (6)$$

It can be shown as in the case of cadmium citrate

complex² that

$$K_1 = \frac{(n-2)[\text{H}^+]}{(3-n)} \quad \dots (7)$$

The values of K_1 are calculated by equation (7) and the mean values of $-\log K_1$ are found to be 4.82 ± 0.15 , 7.48 ± 0.24 , 5.38 ± 0.15 and 5.10 ± 0.06 for beryllium, manganese, nickel and zinc respectively.

The results indicate that the stabilities of the thiomalate complexes of divalent metal ions studied in the present investigation decrease in the order $\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Be}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$ which is in agreement with the observations⁴⁻⁷ made by earlier workers.

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References

1. N. K. MOHANTY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).
2. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 673.
3. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Acta. Chim. Hung.*, 1973, 79, 279.
4. N. K. MOHANTY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 337.
5. G. R. LENZ and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 378.
6. G. E. CHENEY, Q. FERNANDO and H. FREISER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 2055.
7. W. MANCH and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, 38, 192.
8. W. STRICKS, I. M. KOLTHOFF and A. HEYNDRIK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1515.

Some Anionic Complexes of Organometal (III) Derivatives

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A few physico-chemical studies such as electrophoresis anion exchange, paper chromatography have been reported^{1,2} to indicate complexation between organothallium(III) cations and tetraalkyl-ammonium salts. Some organothallium complexes of the general formula $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{PhTlX}_3]$ and $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{PhTlX}_4]$ have also been isolated in the solid state³. Corresponding anions of organometal(III) containing mixed halo-and halo-pseudohalo are not known. This investigation for the first time reports the synthesis and characterisation of such anionic complexes of the formula $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{R}_2\text{MXX}']$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Et, Bu}$; $\text{R}' = \text{Ph or Bu}$; $\text{X and X}' = \text{Cl, Br, I, N}_3 \text{ or NCSe}$).

Experimental

Organometal(III) derivatives R_2MX ($R = \text{Bu}$ or Ph ; $X = \text{Cl}$, N_3 or NCSe ; $M = \text{Ga}$, In or Tl) were prepared by the reported methods^{4,5}.

The new solid organometal(III) complexes have been prepared by the direct interaction of tetraalkylammonium salts with di-organometal(III) compounds.

In a typical experiment, 2.1 g (1 m mole) of tetramethylammonium iodide was dissolved in anhydrous methanol (20 ml) and added dropwise to a stirring suspension of dibutylindium azide (2.7 g, 1 m mole) in methanol (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for about 6 hrs and filtered. The filtrate on concentration yielded pale yellow tetramethylammonium dibutylindium azide iodide which was recrystallised from the same solvent (m.p. 136°). Other complexes were similarly isolated and are listed in Table I.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF DI-ORGANOMETAL (III) MIXED HALO- AND HALO-PSEUDOHALO-ANIONS

Compounds	M. P.	Analysis % Found (Cal.)		
		M	C	H
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{GaClBr}]$	198	17.12 (17.92)	48.21 (47.92)	5.53 (5.49)
$[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{GaClBr}]$	192	12.36 (12.18)	57.82 (57.68)	7.51 (7.89)
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{GaClBr}]$	> 240	15.47 (14.87)	51.11 (51.00)	6.31 (6.37)
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Bu}_2\text{GaSeCNI}]$	> 240	14.20 (14.28)	29.41 (29.38)	6.30 (6.12)
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Bu}_2\text{InClI}]$	112	25.13 (24.48)	31.01 (30.93)	6.48 (6.44)
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Bu}_2\text{InSeCNI}]$	> 240	21.71 (21.53)	29.81 (21.21)	5.70 (5.61)
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Bu}_2\text{InN}_3\text{I}]$	136	25.12 (24.36)	30.82 (30.50)	6.38 (6.35)
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{Bu}_2\text{InN}_3\text{I}]$	> 260	22.44 (21.78)	40.96 (40.90)	7.21 (7.19)
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{TlClBr}]$	164	34.37 (33.80)	39.87 (39.76)	5.01 (4.97)
$[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{TlClBr}]$	> 240	28.67 (28.51)	46.82 (46.96)	6.51 (6.42)
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{TlClI}]$	240d	35.02 (34.31)	32.38 (32.29)	3.76 (3.70)
$[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{Bu}_2\text{TlN}_3\text{I}]$	230d	36.86 (36.36)	25.71 (25.66)	5.51 (5.34)

The products are crystalline solids. They are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents but dissolve in methanol or nitrobenzene. The molar conductance ($24\text{--}29 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) in nitrobenzene corresponds to 1 : 1 electrolyte.

Results and Discussion

Vibrational frequencies associated with the cations are in close agreement to those reported⁶ and are not tabulated. Absorptions associated with the various modes of vibration of pseudohalide groups have been identified. Three absorptions associated with ${}^{\nu}\text{C-Se}$, ${}^{\nu}\text{C-Se}$ and ${}^{\delta}\text{NCSe}$ appear at 2050 cm^{-1} , 660 cm^{-1} and $\sim 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of N-bonded selenocyanate group. Anions containing the azido group also give rise to three absorptions $\sim 2050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 1340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 665 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to asymmetric, symmetric stretchings and bending mode of the covalently bonded, linear $\text{N}=\overset{+}{\text{N}}=\overset{-}{\text{N}}$ group. In the far infrared region absorptions due to $\text{Ga}-\text{C}$, $\text{In}-\text{C}$ and $\text{Tl}-\text{C}$ have been identified at 600 cm^{-1} , 580 cm^{-1} and 570 cm^{-1} respectively which are in good agreement with the reported values⁷⁻⁹. Metal-halogen and metal-nitrogen absorptions lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

The complex anions are therefore ionic in character and on the basis of analytical data, may be formulated as $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{R}'_2\text{MXX}']$, containing tetracoordinated metal atom.

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References

- G. FARAGLIA, A. CASSOL and R. BARBIERI, Proc. Journées Helle'nes de Séparation Immédiate et de Chromatographie (III J. I. S. I. C.) Ass. Greek Chem. Ed., Athens, 1966, 271.
- G. FARAGLIA, L. RONCUCCI FIORANI, B. L. PEPE and R. BARBIERI, Proc. Autumn Meeting, University of Padova, 1966.
- G. FARAGLIA, L. RONCUCCI FIORANI, B. L. PEPE and R. BARBIERI, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1966, 2, 277.
- T. N. SRIVASTAVA and KIRAN KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press).
- A. K. KOCHETKOV and R. KH. FREIDLINA, *Org. Khim.*, 1950, 7, 144.
- Z. MASLOWSKY, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1974, 81, 153.
- M. WILKINSON and I. J. WORRALL, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1975, 93, 39.
- M. J. S. GYNANE and I. J. WORRALL, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1974, 81, 329.
- MINORU TANAKA, HIDEO KUROSAWA and ROKURO OKAWARA, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1967, 3, 565.